

A Quantum Chemical Conformational Study of some Novel Cardiotonic Agents†

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Ethyl 5-cyano-1,6-dihydro-6-oxo-3-pyridine carboxylates are recently reported compounds which exhibit cardiotonic activities. *Ab initio* MO calculations at the STO-3G level on the molecular geometries of three (methyl, isopropyl and tert butyl) 2-substituted analogues of these compounds are reported. The preferred positions in the calculated energy surfaces are compared with their crystal geometries. The results indicate that the substitution pattern at the 2-position is primarily responsible for the cardiotonic potencies of these compounds.

Recent report on the synthesis of some novel heterocyclic compounds, e.g. ethyl 5-cyano-1,6-dihydro-6-oxo-3-pyridine carboxylates with methyl, isopropyl and t-butyl substitutions at the 2-position with significant cardiotonic potency has generated a great interest to the medicinal chemists¹. Although experimental studies to interpret structure-activity relationships on cardiotonic agents have been made earlier^{2,3}, there are very few theoretical studies⁴ to supplement the experimental observations. Thus, in continuation of our interest in the theoretical study of cardiotonic agents⁵ we report here the results of a quantum chemical investigation on the molecular structures of the three 2-substituted analogues of the model compound in an attempt to better understand the structure-activity relationships. The 'model analogue' is shown along with the corresponding dihedral angles in Fig. 1. For the purpose of a geometry optimisation, an initial conformation for this system has been chosen from standard

- 1: R = CH₃,
2: R = CH(CH₃)₂,
3: R = C(CH₃)₃.

Fig. 1

data^{6,7}. *Ab initio* calculations using a minimum basis set (STO-3G) were performed in order to identify not only the minimum energy conformations but also low lying energy conformation of this system.

Method: Calculations were carried out in the STO-3G basis set using 'Berny' optimisation scheme as given in the Gaussian 82 program package⁷. Berny optimisation uses analytically calculated atomic

forces and a guessed force-constant matrix, which is continuously updated during the optimisation, to predict the position of the minimum energy conformation. The calculation of atomic forces generally requires the same duration as the SCF calculation that precedes it. This method of optimisation is very fast and effective for classical, acyclic molecules but may be very slow for molecules with unusual force constants or cyclic structures^{8,9}. Although in our system this method worked reasonably well, geometry optimisations in general by MO programs can not cross energy barriers to find a deeper minimum. The minimum found in a given optimisation is that obtained by decreasing the energy from the starting point. There is therefore no guarantee that the structure obtained would be the global minimum (i.e. the most stable structure), only that it is a stationary point. However, 'Berny' optimisation method can check the nature of the stationary point and since our starting geometry is taken from crystallographic data, the calculated optimised geometry by this method is most likely to be the global minimum structure. Bond lengths and angles (including torsional) were taken from the crystallographic data⁶ and were used for the initial conformation on which full geometry optimisation was performed. Computations were performed on a VAX-11/780 computer in the Institut de Topologie et de Dynamique des Systems de l'Universite Paris, France.

Results and Discussion

In Table 1, the results of the minimum energy conformations of ethyl 5-cyano-1,6-dihydro-2-methyl (isopropyl and tertbutyl)-6-oxo-3-pyridine carboxylate are shown for the STO-3G basis set. For molecules as big as these, STO-3G (three primitive Gaussians per orbital) basis was found to be a good compromise between economy and accuracy.

Our primary interest in the study of energy of 2-alkyl substituted compounds 1-3 with respect to the torsional angle O(9)-C(8)-C(3)-C(2) is to

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TABLE 1—MINIMUM ENERGY CONFORMATION OF ETHYL 5-CYANO-1,6-DIHYDRO-2-R-6-OXO-3-PYRIDINE CARBOXYLATE (1, R=CH₃; 2, R=CH(CH₃)₂; 3, R=C(CH₃)₃)

Selected structural parameters	Fully optimised geometry			Heterocyclic ring and COOR coplanar		
	1	2	3	1	2	3
γ (C ₂ C ₃)	1.487	1.496	1.505	1.498	1.502	1.515
γ (C ₂ C ₄)	1.403	1.410	1.435	1.457	1.445	1.481
γ (C ₂ C ₅)	1.392	1.390	1.398	1.398	1.395	1.415
γ (N ₁ C ₂)	1.354	1.366	1.358	1.388	1.390	1.389
γ (N ₁ C ₆)	1.378	1.375	1.377	1.435	1.436	1.435
γ (C ₆ C ₅)	1.440	1.442	1.435	1.474	1.477	1.468
γ (C ₅ C ₄)	1.364	1.366	1.364	1.375	1.375	1.374
γ (O ₇ C ₆)	1.236	1.234	1.237	1.242	1.238	1.239
γ (C ₂ C ₁₁)	1.435	1.436	1.434	1.440	1.441	1.396
γ (C ₂ C ₁₂)	1.503	1.505	1.504	1.511	1.514	1.512
\angle C ₂ C ₃ N ₁	118.23	117.24	115.96	117.94	117.49	115.72
\angle C ₄ C ₂ C ₃	119.15	120.41	119.97	118.78	117.72	118.03
\angle C ₂ C ₃ C ₅	122.56	121.94	122.88	122.59	124.04	124.50
\angle C ₆ N ₁ C ₂	126.21	126.00	127.38	126.50	127.60	129.31
\angle O ₇ C ₆ N ₁	116.91	116.50	116.62	116.80	116.79	116.90
\angle C ₂ C ₃ C ₂	123.53	123.47	127.02	126.35	128.88	130.77
\angle C ₂ C ₅ O ₇	125.94	125.90	125.86	124.88	124.55	123.43
\angle C ₂ C ₅ O ₁₀	113.38	113.14	113.38	116.98	118.09	120.07
ψ C ₄ C ₂ C ₃ N ₁	-0.38	-0.82	5.13	0.0	0.0	0.0
ψ O ₇ C ₆ C ₂ C ₃	103.78	91.87	78.83	180.0	180.0	180.0
ψ O ₁₀ C ₅ C ₂ C ₃	-77.51	-89.84	-105.33	0.0	0.0	0.0
ψ O ₇ C ₆ N ₁ C ₂	-179.08	179.94	-179.76	180.0	180.0	180.0

TABLE 2—RELATIVE ENERGIES AS FUNCTION OF ψ O₇C₆C₂C₃ ANGLE

Compd.	Relative energy (kcal mol ⁻¹)	
	Heterocyclic ring and COOR coplanar	Optimised torsional angle
1	5.1 (0°)	0.0 (103.8°)
2	8.8 (0°)	0.0 (91.8°)
3	14.5 (0°)	0.0 (78.8°)

determine the 'accessible' conformations which lie close to the global minima, i.e. within a few kcal of the lowest conformers. If needed for biological activity, this extra amount of energy could be supplied by the interaction with the receptor or solvent¹⁰. In Table 2, the results of the relative energies of these compounds as a function of the O(9)–C(8)–C(3)–C(2) torsional angles are shown. The dihedral angles formed by the plane of the carboethoxy moiety and the plane of the heterocyclic ring increases in the order: 1 (5.1) < 2 (8.8) < 3 (14.5 kcal mol⁻¹). The decrease in positive inotropic activity of these three compounds follow exactly an identical trend. This observation not only correlates the three compounds in terms of their potency but also quantifies the steric bulk associated with the compounds. The results are also in agreement with the recently proposed model of positive inotropic activity¹¹. A link between positive inotropic activity and favourable planar conformation has been invoked for several inhibitors, e.g. milrinone⁶, adenosine¹², etc. For milrinone, which is much less active than 1, the STO-3G and 3-21G minimum energy conformations have the pyridine ring at 67° out of plane. About 49.0 kJ mol⁻¹ energy are required to bring the angle to 0 degree. However, the different activity of milrinone with respect

to 1 does not depend only on this energy requirement as the nature of the substituents at the 2 and 3 positions, electronic, hydrophobic and steric properties should also play equally important roles. This view has been fairly well illustrated in an earlier report¹³ on the quantitative analysis of the hydrophobic constant and molar refractivity for methyl, isopropyl and t-butyl substituents which evidences that their values increase in the order t-butyl > isopropyl > methyl, i.e. as the steric bulk increases the positive inotropic activity decreases most probably because the coplanar orientation of the COOR moiety is prevented. Our calculated results of relative energy (Table 2) also indicate a similar trend.

The structure-activity relationship in these compounds is further evaluated through an analysis of charge distribution and dipole moments (Tables 3 and 4). Charge distribution shows that there are two strongly negative and opposing regions corresponding to the N–C=O and O–C=O groups; however, in case of the t-butyl analogue a positively charged zone corresponding to the alkyl

TABLE 3—CHARGE DISTRIBUTION IN SELECTED CENTRES

Atom designations	Charge (e.s.u.)		
	1	2	3
O(9)	-0.37	-0.37	-0.38
C(8)	0.43	0.43	0.42
O(10)	-0.35	-0.35	-0.34
C(3)	-0.24	-0.24	-0.24
C(4)	0.14	0.13	0.13
C(5)	-0.12	-0.12	0.13
C(6)	0.40	0.40	0.40
N(1)	-0.33	-0.33	-0.34
C(2)	0.22	0.24	0.26

TABLE 4—DIPOLE MOMENTS*

1	2	3
6.28 (7.16)	6.35 (7.41)	6.21 (7.60)

*Values within parentheses indicate heterocyclic ring planar.

group is also observed. Thus, for better understanding the biological activity of these molecules, the charge distribution pattern and the effect of torsional angles on the contour maps would be crucial¹⁴. An analysis of the molecular electrostatic potential on these molecules based on the results presented here is being carried out.

Comparison with the crystallographic study: Crystallographic studies as reported⁶ suggest that the heterocyclic ring in these compounds is virtually planar, the deviation from its best mean plane is found in the range -0.025 to 0.023 Å. The $-\text{COO}-$ moiety is rotated to this plane by 32.2° . The most significant feature of the solid state structure is the intermolecular hydrogen bonding between the N-H of the ring of one molecule and the ring carbonyl oxygen of the molecule centrosymmetrically related. The orientation of the carboethoxy moiety with respect to the heterocyclic ring varies in the order 1.7–15.6 for the 2-methyl derivative, 32.2 for the 2-isopropyl derivative and 48.1–49.5 for the 2-t-butyl derivative.

The minimum energy conformations as obtained from the above mentioned computational results are obviously different from those obtained in the solid state due to the forces operating in the crystal lattice. Two main differences are observed from our calculated results: (i) the presence of greater number of conformations with respect to the 'isolated molecule' and (ii) an opposite trend of dihedral angle formed by the plane of the carboethoxy group and that of the heterocyclic ring. However, both crystallography and theoretical calculations indicate the importance of the steric factors due to the substituent at the 2-position, which in the solid state prevents interaction between the 'dimers' of the compounds and in the 'isolated molecules' prevents a coplanar conformation of the COOR group and the heterocyclic ring.

Conclusion: Although the crystallographic observations and the theoretically calculated results on these compounds differ because of obvious reasons the importance of the steric bulk of the substituents at the 2-position is recognised by both the approaches. X-Ray results show that the substituent

at 2-position influences the tilting of the carboethoxy moiety with respect to the heterocyclic ring whereas the theoretical results also show that the 'free' molecules prevent a coplanar conformation of the COOR group and the heterocyclic ring. Thus, the cardiotoxic potency of these molecules is most likely due to reduced conformational flexibility because of the steric bulk at the 2-position. Finally, if a molecular recognition pattern of the molecules were to be derived for understanding their pharmacological behaviour, the effect of the orientation of the COOR group with respect to the heterocyclic ring would be extremely significant. Electrostatic potential on the molecules are currently undertaken.

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